

Exploring the Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Enhancing Innovation Management Process: A Case of Kazakhstan Higher Education Sector

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Abstract - The primary goal of the research is to explore the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in Kazakhstan and its implication in innovation management, focusing on higher education institutions. The research would enhance the effectiveness of artificial intelligence and the potential positive impact on developing innovative management in the education sector. Regression, correlation, and descriptive analysis were conducted for some variables in analyzing the research dataset. The research contained six variables, one of which was dependent and five of which were independent variables. The scholars gleaned data from 206 country-wide faculty members with the support of a questionnaire after checking the reliability and validity with McDonald Omega and KMO. The teaching method of higher education institutions has a crucial influence on the effectiveness and combines all teaching tasks, such as material quality, visual presentation, and accurate answers. It explains that the young generation frequently manages the demand for service innovation with artificial innovation.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Higher education institutions, Innovation management, McDonald Omega and KMO, Kazakhstan.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, society actively monitors the development of technology. Many technologies include artificial intelligence, which actively enters every person's daily routine. Artificial intelligence is an information system capable of thinking, calculating, searching, and imitating the consciousness of a natural person. Artificial intelligence has become a universal tool and has covered many areas of society. According to various international reports, Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIEd) is an emerging field in educational technology. It has broad advantages in making pedagogical design significantly impact teaching and learning in higher education [1]. The entire world of academia confidently uses artificial intelligence irrespective of the disciplines; from all fields of engineering, business, and basic sciences to humanities, many students use artificial intelligence as a learning instrument and a helping tool for acquiring knowledge.

The chosen research topic is relevant, as it affects artificial intelligence, a modern tool many areas can no longer do without. The development of innovative management in the Kazakhstani service sector is not as active as that of artificial intelligence. However, there is a clear opinion that if artificial intelligence is introduced as a tool for development in innovation management, it will positively impact the operational process. The concentration fell on the choice of a specific service area education. The ongoing research should help people in the field of education to be open to introducing artificial intelligence. It is essential to show what impact and action will have from introducing artificial intelligence into innovation management in education. The main point is also to show what benefits academia in educational institutions will receive from introducing artificial intelligence into the education process. As mentioned earlier, artificial intelligence has covered many areas of everyone's life. In particular, the sphere of innovation management has not been ignored. Innovation management is one of the parts of strategic management responsible for creativity and introducing ideas and new products. People react differently to introducing something new into an already established working process. Many people, especially the adult generation, were skeptical about the advent of artificial intelligence. Their point of view can be understood because artificial intelligence has been on the market for a short time, but it is already actively popular in various fields.

The consistent rise of artificial intelligence applications in education is evident and received significant attention from academia in the last couple of years. AI and adaptive learning technologies are prominently featured as essential developments in educational technology in the 2018 Horizon report [2], with a time to adoption of 2 or 3 years. According to the report, experts anticipate AI in education to grow 43 percent in 2018–2022. However, the Horizon Report 2019 Higher Education Edition [3] predicts that AI applications related to teaching and learning are projected to grow even more significantly than this. Even with the immense prospects that AI might provide to back teaching and learning, recent ethical consequences and threats come in with the development of AI claims in higher education. The study's primary purpose is to understand how the development of artificial intelligence affects innovation management in the education sector of Kazakhstan. In the study, it is necessary to note both the positive and negative sides of artificial intelligence's influence on innovation management.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The first time the word artificial intelligence was used was by John McCarthy, who conducted a workshop at Dartmouth College in the USA in 1956 [4]. The study of artificial intelligence continues to center on the assumption that every aspect of learning or any other feature of astuteness can be so wholly depicted that a machine can be presented to replicate it. An effort will be made to make machines use language, form abstractions and concepts, solve problems now engaged for humans, and improve themselves. A comprehensive definition of artificial intelligence (AI) was offered: "Computers which perform cognitive tasks, usually associated with human minds, particularly learning and problem-solving" [5]. They explained that AI does not describe a single technology. It is an umbrella term to describe a range of technologies and methods, such as machine learning, natural language processing, data mining, neural networks, or an algorithm. With the innovation of AIED and the accessibility of (big) student data and learning analytics, [6] claim a "renaissance in assessment." AI can grant just-in-time response and evaluation. Instead of stop-and-test, AIED can be constructed to realize actions to continue examining student accomplishment. Algorithms have been employed to guess the likelihood of a student failing an assignment or dropping out of a course with high levels of accuracy [7]. In their latest article [8], the advanced educational AI tools are from three distinct viewpoints: a) learner-facing, b) teacher-facing, and c) system-facing artificial intelligence in education (AIED). Learner-facing AI tools are software students use to learn a subject matter, i.e., adaptive or personalized learning management systems or ITS. Teacher-facing systems support teachers and reduce their workload by automating tasks such as administration, assessment, feedback, and plagiarism detection. Artificial intelligence in education (AIED) tools also provide insight into students' learning progress so that the teacher can proactively offer support and guidance where needed. System-facing AIED are tools that provide information for administrators and managers on the institutional level, for instance, to monitor attrition patterns across faculties or colleges. The most influential advanced technologies, artificial intelligence, and machine learning (ML) are mechanisms developed from data management and evolution processes. Implementing these in different businesses is a recent trend in many industries or sectors, including education, which have been identified as game-changers.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) evolved from data management and developing processes. Incorporating these mechanisms into business is a trend many industries, including education, have identified as game-changers. Consequently, education platforms in general and the higher education sector introduced these novel technologies as prime applications, more closely aligned with learners' needs and knowledge, making the educational process more efficient. Hence, AI and ML have magnificent potential in e-learning and higher education institutions (HEI). A comprehensive research was initiated to study implementation opportunities and challenges higher education institutions face using

artificial intelligence and machine learning. The study depicted comprehensively crucial matters, corresponding to shared knowledge and attitude of study bases regarding AI and ML in higher education institutions; unsurpassed executes concerning practice, students' knowledge, and students' perspectives regarding AI and ML opportunities and challenges in higher education institutions. The results indicated that artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are vital bits of knowledge or technologies that augment learning, primarily through students' skills, collaborative learning in higher education institutions, and a manageable research setting [9]. A similar kind of research was conducted in India with the aim of how the emergence of the use and application of artificial intelligence in higher education has opened new possibilities and challenges. The research proved that the use of AI in higher institutions would bring in notable change concerned with how teachers would enrich them with competent knowledge improvement, how students would learn by tapping diverse sources, and how accurate and prompt decisions can be taken in the institutes of higher learning [10]. Another exciting research exclusively studied the influence of artificial intelligence on online learning in higher institutions. It enunciated that AI has brought novel methods for improving instruction and learning in the online mode of knowledge transfer [11].

The primary goal of the research is to explore the role of artificial intelligence in the Kazakhstan market and its implications in innovation management, with a prior focus on the educational centers' service sector. For the past years, the theme of artificial intelligence has been the most exciting and investigated because of its benefits in the automation of some business processes and in enhancing companies' overall performance and productivity. The effect of artificial intelligence on innovation is represented as the 'invention of a method invention,' which means that one innovation generates another [12]. Education services around the world have improved with the integration of artificial intelligence. It increased the productivity of the operation process and helped focus more on the quality of the service by using innovative tools. These are creating intelligent content, voice assistants, personalized learning systems, closing skill gaps, etc. [13]. Companies integrating to level up their services as tangible examples of using artificial intelligence (AI) can be Google, Coursera, and Duolingo—the Google Classroom, widely used among educational centers to design and assess tasks by providing feedback. With Google Translate and Scholar, the barriers in the language and analyzing research papers decreased. It is the same with the Duolingo and Coursera programs, which help to develop flexible learning and make online learning easy [13]. Therefore, the impact of artificial intelligence in education is increasing and helps to generate new ways of vision in learning. In the case of the education sector of Kazakhstan, the study tries to identify the current effectiveness of the centers' services and what factors have the primary influence on providing sufficient service. It can be assumed that general educational institutions' effectiveness is high enough according to the literacy rate of the Kazakhstan population, which is 99.80 percent [14]. Then, the factors affecting the service's effectiveness in Kazakhstan's education institutions can be developed and explored through artificial intelligence. The further purpose of the study is to understand how artificial intelligence is used in the educational service sector and what kind of effect it has on the overall performance and effectiveness of services. The research assesses the current situation of education services and their integration rate with the country. The study includes learning tools to integrate AI, such as chatbots for communications, presentation generators, and automotive homework checkers. As a crucial part of the study, the educational institutions in Kazakhstan were subjects to analyze, including systems with AI integration and traditional perspective of service. Therefore, the end goal of the study is to identify best practices for implementation and patterns for service delivery. Through the comprehensive analysis, the research results provide recent and valuable information for all centers that work in educational services as a decision-making tool to improve the effectiveness of the services in Kazakhstan.

The study's primary purpose is to identify the effectiveness of the service in educational centers by integrating Artificial intelligence and to decrease the operational process to enhance the quality of service provided through innovation management in Kazakhstan. A regression analysis assessed how organizations manage their service and foster innovation. For the study, the following six variables have been considered:

- X1. The effectiveness rate of the education service
- X2. The effectiveness rate of teaching methods
- X3. The presence of technology integration
- X4: Accessibility of online and offline presence
- X5: Number of students per month
- X6: Familiarity with Artificial Intelligence

Additionally, for the descriptive analysis, the gender, age, and city of presence were collected. The AI services list included a presentation generator, automatic homework check, and chatbot to analyze the most helpful tool for current business.

Hypothesis Chosen: Hypothesis for this study that thoroughly explains the purpose of the study.

H1: The introduction of artificial intelligence has a positive impact on the development of innovative management in the field of education.

H0: The introduction of artificial intelligence has a negative impact on the development of innovative management in the field of education.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Several types of studies were considered to analyze the information obtained. Based on the information received and the purpose of the study, the choice fell on a descriptive study. Study participants took part without pressure and of their own free will. Information was collected through a questionnaire using Google Forms. This method helped collect information necessary for the study and received the participants' opinions. The study aims to understand what impact artificial intelligence can have on optimizing the work of an educational center. The nature of the research is descriptive and exploratory, with correlation analysis also present.

The study was conducted among teachers and tutors of higher educational institutions in Kazakhstan. Two hundred six people from all regions of Kazakhstan took part in the survey, 155 of them women and 51 men. The age range of the participants varies from 19 to 55 years old. The information was collected through a questionnaire using the Google Forms platform. The data was collected from primary sources due to the specifics of the chosen topic for research. Finding secondary information on artificial intelligence's impact on educational institutions' innovative management was difficult. Based on this, it was decided to collect information manually from the primary sources. Thanks to the primary information, you can get information needed for research and further analysis. The information obtained from primary sources is also relevant, fresh, and relevant to the chosen topic. This information will be appropriate during the study. As mentioned earlier, the information was collected through a questionnaire. The Google Forms platform came to the rescue in creating the questionnaire.

The questionnaire contains eleven questions. An unlimited number of people could take the questionnaire, and there were several answer options for a more convenient survey passage. The questionnaire allows you to collect information from people of various ages from different parts of the

country. As a dependent variable, the effectiveness rate of the higher education institutions and independent variables were chosen, such as teaching methods, technology presence, online and offline accessibility, number of clients per month, and familiarity with artificial intelligence. The correlation showed a higher effectiveness rate with the teaching method, technology presence, and many clients by 34, 20, and 23 percent, respectively. Through regression analysis, several models were chosen as the two best models. In descriptive statistics, the average effectiveness rate in Kazakhstan was 3.3, which was in the neutral position.

Moreover, you can add questions to the questionnaire, the answers to which will help in the study. Therefore, participation in the questionnaire is anonymous and confidential. Hence, participants take the survey honestly and openly. Research is aimed at helping teachers and facilitating the process of their work, so honesty and openness are essential here. When creating the questionnaire, it was taken into account that the questionnaire would be sent to teachers and tutors of higher educational institutions. Therefore, it was essential to take into account the age, gender, and location of the participants. Two hundred six teachers took part in the survey, and it was decided that this was a sufficient number of survey participants concerning the total number of teachers of educational centers in the country. When creating the questionnaire, it was essential to choose the correct sample size, which is included in this sample, as this directly affects the course of the study. It was taken into account that the questionnaire would be sent to teachers and tutors at educational institutions. Therefore, it was essential to take into account the age, gender, and location of the participants.

The researchers administered stratified and convenience sampling methods to glean the data from two hundred and fifty. However, the investigators received two hundred and six within a stipulated time. They decided that this was a sufficient number of survey participants concerning the total number of faculty from all disciplines of educational centers in the country. The questionnaire was conducted online and distributed through various communication channels. The questionnaire was sent in multiple ways, through acquaintances in the field of education, to get the right audience. The survey was also sent to the Instagram profiles of educational centers. The questionnaire is a convenient format for obtaining information for those who take the survey. The study's primary purpose, as mentioned earlier, is to understand the impact of the introduction of artificial intelligence on the development of innovative management in the field of education. The focus of the study is to understand the reaction to the introduction of artificial intelligence by potential users. Besides, the study identified the reasons that affect the effectiveness of higher educational institutions in administering diverse technologies, especially artificial intelligence. "How would you rate the effectiveness of your education service?" This question was asked to understand how effective the teachers/tutors consider their work to be. Only 31% of respondents replied that they rated the offered service by 5 points. The remaining 163 survey participants rate the service they provide much less. "Do you use modern technologies in your service?" This question helps to understand teachers' attitudes and technical equipment to new technologies.

What is encouraging is that 119 people out of the respondents replied that they use new technologies in their work. "Are you familiar with artificial intelligence services?" This question helps to understand how well the intended users of artificial intelligence are familiar with the concept of this term. 46.6% of the respondents replied that they were unfamiliar with the concept of artificial intelligence. Based on this, it is also crucial in this study to show the benefits of using artificial intelligence to optimize the process. "Of the following services, which one do you consider the most helpful for your service?". Several possible answers were offered to this question, and the survey participants chose the most beneficial artificial intelligence tool according to their version. Eighty-seven (87) out of 206 respondents believe that generating presentations based on the information provided is the most helpful tool. "Would

you like to implement artificial intelligence? into the work of your service?" This question was used to understand the reaction of potential users to the introduction of artificial intelligence in optimizing their work process, and 87.1% of respondents agreed that they were ready to introduce artificial intelligence into their work.

Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the information received. The information collected through Google Forms has been converted into a file. According to how much Excel works with numbers, converting the categorical variable into a numerical variable was necessary. The analysis was carried out using descriptive, correlation, and regression analyses. First, a descriptive analysis was performed for Y variables, which is an assessment of the effectiveness of the service at the moment. Descriptive analysis was also provided for the variable of working online/offline. The analysis helped determine who has more online and offline centers or those use only one format. Another descriptive analysis was also conducted to identify the most popular service provided by artificial intelligence for narrative centers. This analysis was carried out to obtain an average efficiency value. Secondly, the categorical variables were converted to digital values. The analysis has one categorical variable -artificial intelligence's most helpful service for an educational center. Thirdly, the primary variable Y was selected, and steel variable X affected changes and deviations in variable Y. Seven different models were created to determine which of the variables X had the most decisive influence on Y. Multiple regressions were performed on each model to identify the three best models and continue the research based on them.

As a result, in each regression, you need to consider adjusted R^2 to compare and select the models with the highest indicator.

Model 1: Effectiveness of Service (Y), Opinion about teaching Methods (X), number of clients per month(X).

Model 2: Effectiveness of Service (Y), use of modern technologies (X), number of clients per month(X).

Correlation analysis was used to understand the relationship between variables. The effectiveness of the service includes four factors that influence the effectiveness: teaching methods, use of modern technologies, ability to teach online and offline, number of clients per month, and awareness of the artificial intelligence concept.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The perusal of this section emphasized the demographic profile of the respondents, the reliability and validity of the instrument, the testing hypothesis, and a comprehensive discussion of the study's outcome.

A. Demographics of Respondents

The study involved 206 people, 51 male and 155 female. As a percentage, this is 24.40 percent male and 75.60 percent female. Coming to age, the age range from 31 to 35 is the highest; 65 people took part in this age range, which is a percentage of 31.50 percent. The age range from 26 to 30 is in second place; 56 participants in this age range took part. As a percentage, it is equal to 27.19 percent. The age range from 34 to 40 years is the third place. Forty-one people of this age category took part; as a percentage, it is 20 respondents. In fourth place is the age range from 19 to 25 years old. Thirteen people participated in this age group, with a percentage of 6.31 percent. The smallest number of participants in

the age group from 46 to 55 years old, only eight people took part, which is a percentage of 3.88. Participants from all over Kazakhstan took part in the survey.

TABLE 1
DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE SUBJECTS

.No.	Demographic Feature	Frequency	Percentage
.	Gender		
	Male	51	24.40
	Female	155	75.60
	Total	206	100.00
.	Age		
	19-25	13	06.31
	26-30	56	27.19
	31-35	65	31.55
	36-40	41	19.90
	41-45	23	11.17
	46-55	8	03.88
	Total	206	100.00
.	Country Region		
	North	42	20.39
	East	08	3.88
	West	14	6.80
	South	132	64.08
	Central	10	4.85
	Total	206	100.00

Source: Research findings

The most significant percentage of participation was from Southern Kazakhstan, which is equal to 64.08 percent. One hundred thirty-two residents of Southern Kazakhstan took part in the study. Residents of Northern Kazakhstan did not stay away; 42 residents took part in the survey. As a percentage, this is equal to 20.90 percent of the total number of participants. Fourteen Western Kazakhstan residents also participated in the study; the percentage is 6.80. Ten people from central Kazakhstan took part, which is 4.85 percent. In fifth place, eight East Kazakhstan residents participated in the survey. In percentage terms, it is equal to 3.88.

B. Reliability/validity test of the questionnaire

According to the statistical summary, most businesses rated their service effectiveness as effective and productive. On average, the strategy's effectiveness within Kazakhstan equals 3.6, and some businesses rated their service effectiveness as very ineffective. Therefore, other factors should be considered and implemented to increase the service's effectiveness rate. In the case of the study, artificial intelligence can be the crucial factor to change the rate positively.

The survey results showed the number of participants in the market online and offline. The model for this variable was 0, representing that most of them do not present the service online, and it affected identifying the relationship between the variables. Most businesses with many clients have online and

offline presence in the market. Before introducing the questionnaire through Google Forms to glean the information from the faculty of Kazakhstan, the investigators checked the reliability and validity by administering McDonald Omega and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) tests; the test results were 0.89 and 0.82, respectively.

The challenges businesses face in communication with clients are that as the number of clients increases, the information to process increases, taking the focus away from one side. Other challenges included preparing the material for presentation and automatic homework checking, which decreased the operational process. The most helpful service was chosen by the response result selected as generating presentations based on the information provided, after, chatbots for automatic recording of the client and embedding information into the database with 38.2 percent of all proportions. Before the regression analysis, the correlation was constructed to know which variables would be used and what effect each of them had. The range of the correlation was between 13 and 34 percent, representing a positive effect on the service's effectiveness. The teaching method variable had a 34 percent positive impact on the dependent variable, and the variables' explanations and relations to each other were sufficient. Technology usage and online and offline presence had a 20 and 14 percent of the correlation. The presence of the technology had a positive impact on the service productivity. The overall performance of an efficient business is explained by the number of clients and the positive relations to 23 percent in the correlation table. The lowest correlation of the variables comes from familiarity with Artificial Intelligence, with a 13 percent correlation with the dependent variable. Therefore, for further analysis, three variables would significantly affect the service: technological presence, number of clients, and teaching methods.

C. Testing of Hypothesis

Further analysis focuses on regression, where six (6) variables were chosen to identify the relations and effects of the educational service and Artificial Intelligence usage. The variables contain dependent and independent variables. As dependent variables in the data were chosen, the effectiveness of the current service and four (4) variables of independent variable.

After the selection of the variable, the models were constructed. Overall, eight models were tested, and the following criteria chose the best three (3) models:

1. The adjusted R^2 percentage should be sufficient for further explanation.
2. The model should qualify the right to exist by the significance F in the ANOVA table. The qualification was approved through significance F and significance level. If the significance level is greater than the significance F, then the model has the right to exist, and one variable is not equal to zero. The significance level equals to 0.05 or 5 percent.
3. The last step in choosing the model was verifying each variable—the verification was approved through P value and significance level. If the p-value were smaller than the significance level, then the variable would explain the dependent variable.

The first model out of three had two variables: categorical value with the rate of teaching method effectiveness and the second one was the number of clients per month. According to the results of the summary output, the statistics in regression showed 14 percent of R^2 and adjusted R^2 was 13 percent, meaning 14 percent of the variation was explained by the teaching method and number of clients per month. The proportion was insufficient; however, the resulting output can be used compared to others. The significance is that F had the right to exist, and one variable was not equal to zero. The last step, testing the

intercept, teaching method, and a number of the client variables, was significant and explained the dependent variable. Therefore, the model had the following output:

- * Effectiveness of the service = $2.44 + \beta_1 * \text{teaching method} + \beta_2 * \text{number of the clients}$
- * Effectiveness of the service = $2.44 + 0.27 * \text{teaching method} + 0.003 * \text{number of the clients}$

The effectiveness of the service with the two variables had a high starting point of 2.44. The good-created teaching method increases to 0.27, and with additional clients, the effectiveness increases by 0.003. The effect from the number of clients is relatively slow; however, it adds value to the rate. The second model was constructed with two variables: technology usage for service and the number of clients. The first variable was categorical with the "yes and no" value, and it was converted to the numerical value, where yes was one (1) and no was 0. In the summary output regression statistics, the R^2 showed 7%, and the adjusted R^2 output is the same.

In comparison with the first model, the proportion of the variation was two times low, which could have happened due to the limited response number—the 7 percent of the variation service effectiveness explained by the technology usage and number of clients. The significance level had the right to exist, and the variables were significant. Therefore, the model had the following output: * Effectiveness of the service = $3.32 + \beta_1 * \text{usage of technology for the service} + \beta_2 * \text{number of the clients}$; * Effectiveness of the service = $3.32 + 0.24 * \text{usage of technology for the service} + 0.003 * \text{number of the clients}$.

The model's starting point was higher than the first one, and the effect of variables was similar. Technology usage positively affected the service effectiveness and would increase to 0.24 if technology was integrated. The third model used a variable teaching method and familiarity with artificial intelligence. The R^2 for the model equals 13 percent, and the adjusted R^2 of 12 percent is the proportion by which the independent variables explain the dependent variables. The significance is that F had the right to exist, and one variable did not equal zero. According to the last summary output statistics, the intercept and teaching method was sufficient, while the familiarity was insufficient. It happened because the answer contained two choices. Therefore, the model had the following output: * Effectiveness of the service = $2.35 + \beta_1 * \text{teaching method} + \beta_2 * \text{familiarity with Artificial Intelligence}$; * Effectiveness of the service = $2.35 + 0.29 * \text{teaching method} + 0.17 * \text{familiarity with Artificial Intelligence}$. The regression results show that the teaching method significantly influenced service effectiveness, and familiarity with the AI could increase the effectiveness by 0.17 points.

By summarizing the results of the analysis, it can be seen that educational services heavily rely on the operational process and integration of technological innovation. The survey participants favor the implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) because it can enhance the productivity of each operational process and opens opportunities to improve the quality. Therefore, the research hypothesis, "the introduction of artificial intelligence has a positive impact on the development of innovative management in the field of education," is proven because managing innovation through artificial intelligence has a positive impact. Moreover, the implementation brings benefits such as better communication with the clients, which would increase the capacity, providing valuable material preparation, which increases the quality of education and leads to satisfied customer feedback. The automatic functions of the operational process would improve the managing process and increase accuracy. To increase the number of clients, most institutions focused on offline presence more; however, communication was the factor that had the right to develop. 36.2 percent of the responses mentioned that the service would help improve communication tools. The technology implication is primarily used in the more prominent institutions and the users ages 23-35 years.

V. FINDINGS

A. The current service effectiveness of the company within Kazakhstan is, on average, 3.3, which represents a neutral position where it is insufficient, and with the implication of artificial intelligence integration, it would increase the situation to 0.17 with the enhancing scale of presence.

B. The technology implication is mainly used in the more prominent centers; the owner is between 23 and 35 years old. It explains that the young generation frequently manages the demand for service innovation.

C. The teaching method of the service has a crucial influence on the effectiveness and combines all teaching tasks, such as material quality, visual presentation, and accurate answers. Therefore, these tasks can be done with artificial intelligence (AI), and the participants focus on integrating into the business.

D. To increase the number of clients, most businesses focus on offline presence more; however, the factor that has the right to develop is communication. 36.2 percent of the responses mentioned that the service would help improve communication tools. Respondents face the challenge of integrating chatbots for automatic response, chatting with the client immediately, recording the client, and collecting client feedback.

E. The southern part of the country, by 64.10 percent, especially Almaty, has an enormous number of participants in educational service, raising competition, which leads to a focus on competitive advantages. Additionally, statistics show that centers with the most clients use technology and online presence, differentiating them from others. Therefore, the integration of artificial intelligence could be used as a tremendous competitive advantage with the new teaching method or interesting app recommendation.

VI. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

The development of the field of education is beneficial for the state. Artificial intelligence optimizes many processes, including optimizing the learning process and preparing classes for teachers, which has a beneficial effect on the development of the field of education. Entrepreneurs in educational institutions: The founders of educational centers benefit most from introducing artificial intelligence. Thanks to artificial intelligence, entrepreneurs can save money on a manager who will keep records and a customer base. Artificial intelligence can also keep the center's accounting records. It turns out that the entrepreneur will also save on the accountant's salary. With the introduction of artificial intelligence into work, the faculty of educational institutions will make life much easier for the entire faculty community. Artificial intelligence can create high-quality presentations and analyze the information received. So, artificial intelligence can check homework and test assignments in a short span of time. You can also use artificial intelligence to keep an attendance log, which will be done automatically. Artificial intelligence can also generate various games and training by analyzing the lesson material. Even the learning community has many benefits from applying recent technologies like artificial intelligence, chatbots, and higher education institutions. Implementing artificial intelligence into educational centers directly impacts the clients of the same center. Artificial intelligence optimizes recording the lesson and scheduling classes, which will be convenient for both the student and the teacher. Also, the introduction of artificial intelligence is great for introverted clients. The chatbot will record quickly and without unnecessary words and questions.

The recommendations for the teaching community and higher education institution think-tank start from the planning strategy with artificial intelligence integration to emphasize the tool's full potential in innovation management and capacity. Integrating such tools takes time and would serve for a while, and

planning out all the points can help discover more efficient ways to use them. The different stakeholders of the education sector, particularly faculty and students, have an opportunity to create partnership relations with the company, focusing on technological advancement and connecting business to continuous improvement. The partnership would benefit from the point that the first service would be offered to you, leading to being the prominent ambassador of technological advancement and fast-speed integration. Additionally, the quality and efficiency of service work would be in the partners' hands. To focus on the data that would drive a qualified decision-making process. The data could be collected through integration programs with artificial intelligence, providing valuable information on client satisfaction, current trends, and industry analysis. Moreover, it could suggest different leadership ways and predict more accurate information.

VII. CONCLUSION, LIMITATIONS, AND SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

A. Closing Remarks and Recommendations

The research focuses on exploring the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing the innovation management process in Kazakhstan's service sector, with a primary focus on educational services shows great perspectives for positive improvements. The research results provide opportunities to develop service to a convenient level because the current effectiveness rate of the service is in a neutral position. The study found that integrating artificial intelligence predicts an increase in the scope of presence and creates additional innovative competitive advantage. The study identified the trend that technology implications are widely used in large centers, and the owners of such centers are mainly in the 23- 35 years range. It highlights the active engagement of the young generations in education and its expansion.

Additionally, the teaching method is crucial to improving effectiveness and integration. Artificial intelligence would be a valid solution in automating tasks such as quality of material, visual presentation, and accuracy in answer checking. Furthermore, the research admits the importance of communication and the need to develop unique tools. About 40 percent of participants confirmed that the business needs integration chatbots, which automatically would respond and make conversation with the client by collecting feedback and recording the client to the system in case of a favorable decision. Therefore, the study confirms that the introduction of artificial intelligence has a positive impact on the development of innovative management in the field of education. By considering the long-term success of the service sector, innovation management can focus on artificial intelligence and maximize output results while saving time and ensuring the accuracy of the information.

In conclusion, the research findings suggest that the Kazakhstan service sector would benefit from focusing on managing innovation through Artificial Intelligence. The skilled implementation of this tool opens the opportunity for automation, analysis and prediction, cost saving, research accuracy, and personalization. The integration of artificial intelligence promises the start of a new innovative future by leading the market. Despite the limitations, the research provides a significant analysis of the topic of study. The research can be used by people interested in educational services to outline the benefits of integrating artificial intelligence. The findings provide valuable information on how to increase the capacity of current effectiveness, and the recommendations shared would give direction on how to focus and develop for future potential.

B. Limitations of the Study

The limitations of the research encountered during the work: Firstly, due to the choice of a specific research topic, namely the introduction of artificial intelligence into the innovative management of educational institutions in Kazakhstan. The topic has a narrow focus, so the search for information took longer than planned, and the scholars faced the fact that there was not much information in general. Secondly, there is a problem with collecting information. Many people to whom the survey was sent ignored it. Besides, many could answer incorrectly without delving into the questions' essence. This has a direct impact on the course of the study. As a result, the research result may be inaccurate and irrelevant. Thirdly, due to the specifics of the topic, it took more time to collect data since it takes much more time to get information from so many teachers. Finally, the Opinion of the survey participants may change. Their change is not recorded in the study, affecting the relevance of the information and the entire study.

C. Scope for Further Research

The study focuses only on one service sector and concludes by integrating educational services. For that reason, the study should explore other service sectors by identifying potential opportunities, challenges, and the overall impact of artificial intelligence on effectiveness and productivity. The sample size can be enlarged from students to the CEOs of the different organizations. More focus is placed on identifying the strength of the tools and a broader vision for implementation by analyzing global practices and testing the project's feasibility. Part of the research can explore the barriers or limitations of artificial intelligence and what barriers exist to adopting the tool. The theme of risk management and green management in innovation would be beneficial because ethics should hold a place in the business sphere.

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